

Studies in the Absorption Spectra of Acetoacetarylamides, Hydroxyquinolines and their Methylene bis-Derivatives

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Absorption spectra in the ultra-violet region of the substituted amides of acetoacetic acid and their corresponding α, α' -methylene bis-derivatives as well as of the hydroxy quinolines and their corresponding, 3,3'-methylene bis-derivatives have been studied. In each of these pairs (mono and bis), it is observed, that the bis-compounds showed hyperchromic effect by the rise in the absorption intensity over each of the mono compounds respectively.

RAMART-LUCAS, Naik and Trivedi¹ studied absorption in the ultraviolet of malon aryl-amides and Naik, Trivedi, Mehta and Mankad^{2,3} in further extension of the work, have studied absorption spectra of dichloro malon arylamides and of acetoacet arylamides.

Insulation effect, among others, is one of the effects which influence the development of the absorption spectrum, in which two or more chromophores or auxochromes exist in the same molecule, but are separated from each other by insulating groups, and there can be no effective interaction between them. Venkatraman⁴ observed that when two chromophores are separated by $-\text{CH}_2-$ group, which break the

that of the simple compound and observed that both the curves are identical. Ghosh, Ganguly and Bhattacharya⁵ have thrown some light on the absorption spectra of isoquinoline and its methylene-bis-derivative.

Piper and Brode⁷ have observed in some dyes, that in the conjugation coupling there appears to be a multiplication effect. Braude⁸ pointed out that the interaction between the unsaturated electrons of groups separated by one or more saturated carbon atoms is too weak to affect the spectral properties.

A number of mono and bis-derivatives have been investigated in the present work with a view to observe the magnitude of insulation effect produced in the

Fig. 1

conjugation and act as insulators between the two electronic oscillators. Corley and Blout⁵ gave the spectrum of dinaphthylmethane in comparison with

bis-compounds by the intervening $-\text{CH}_2-$ group between the two identical parts of the same molecule. In a few simpler cases Friedel and Orchin⁹ have drawn attention to this effect, but none of them appear to have the structure of a bis-derivative. It

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TABLE 1—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF METHYLENE BIS-(ACETOACET ARYLAMIDES) AND OF ACETOACET ARYLAMIDES

λ°	Log E															
	1'	1	2'	2	3'	3	4'	4	5'	5	6'	6	7'	7	8'	8
2400	—	—	4.854	3.974	4.460	4.227	4.383	4.075	—	—	4.465	4.325	—	—	—	—
2600	4.305	3.976	4.530	3.712	4.441	4.197	4.217	3.825	4.638	3.988	4.360	4.210	4.207	3.832	4.841	4.134
2800	3.983	3.677	4.583	3.621	4.170	3.868	3.978	3.660	4.273	3.648	4.107	3.787	4.355	3.980	4.722	4.162
3000	3.755	3.361	4.378	3.387	3.894	3.583	3.705	3.385	4.018	3.334	3.863	3.532	4.338	3.943	4.590	4.045
3200	3.618	3.075	4.332	3.232	3.761	3.355	3.546	3.210	3.887	3.158	3.709	3.175	4.140	3.750	4.286	3.706
3400	3.524	2.962	4.240	3.130	3.627	3.270	3.446	3.140	3.186	3.078	3.523	3.075	3.725	3.420	4.150	3.600
3600	3.412	2.850	3.987	3.046	3.473	3.170	3.330	3.030	3.688	2.961	3.397	2.965	3.593	3.180	4.047	3.437
3800	3.338	2.793	3.851	2.960	3.415	3.078	3.290	2.935	3.628	2.875	3.305	2.898	3.491	3.044	4.003	3.193
4000	3.263	2.728	3.761	2.900	3.377	3.017	3.251	2.857	3.631	2.800	3.226	2.846	3.450	2.952	3.960	3.072

TABLE 2—EXTINCTION COEFFICIENT OF 3,3'-METHYLENE BIS-(2-HYDROXY-4-METHYL)QUINOLINES AND OF 2-HYDROXY-4-METHYLQUINOLINES

λ°	log E											
	1'	1	2'	2	3'	3	4'	4	5'	5	6'	6
2400	—	—	4.640	4.200	—	—	—	—	—	—	4.587	4.554
2600	4.691	3.914	4.495	3.853	4.531	4.150	4.430	3.749	4.619	3.955	4.384	4.337
2800	4.544	3.774	4.420	3.890	4.516	4.165	4.517	3.834	4.642	4.020	4.583	4.340
3000	4.370	3.607	4.203	3.504	4.316	3.950	4.303	3.419	4.425	3.760	4.232	3.935
3200	4.435	3.837	4.190	3.750	4.356	3.978	4.287	3.583	4.564	3.974	4.098	3.775
3400	4.293	3.725	4.100	3.797	4.286	3.901	4.380	3.680	4.490	3.936	4.045	3.782
3600	3.842	2.773	3.790	3.255	3.900	3.550	4.077	3.347	3.870	3.150	4.016	3.729
3800	3.755	2.690	3.650	2.895	3.783	3.450	3.645	2.808	3.768	3.063	3.866	3.216
4000	3.755	2.726	3.557	2.819	3.701	3.362	3.597	2.728	3.731	3.016	3.627	3.016

Fig. 2

was, therefore, of interest to examine the relevant pairs of the absorption spectra of several acetoacet arylamides and hydroxy quinolines as well as of their corresponding methylene bis-derivatives.

The extinction coefficient values E of these compounds and the mean at various wave lengths in the ultra-violet region are shown. It would be noticed

that the bis-compounds show a hyperchromic effect over each of the curves having simpler 'half molecule' member. In class (A) compounds of acetoacet series the values of the E ratio for each of the pairs (mono and bis) are shown in Table 1; and those of class (B) compounds in quinoline series are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 3

The curves of class (A) compounds on plates I to IV are (1) Acetoacet anilide, (2) Acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, (3) Acetoacet-*p*-toluidide, (4) Acetoacet-1 : 2 : 4-xyli-
dide, (5) Acetoacet-*o*-chloroanilide, (6) Acetoacet-*m*-
chloroanilide, (7) Acetoacet- α -naphthylamide and
(8) Acetoacet- β -naphthylamide, as well as their corre-
sponding methylene bis-derivatives (1' to 8'),

The curves of class (B) compounds on plates V to VIII are (1) 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl quinoline, (2) 2-Hydroxy-4,6-dimethylquinoline, (3) 2-Hydroxy-4,8-dimethylquinoline, (4) 2-Hydroxy-4,6,8-trimethylquinoline (5) 2-Hydroxy-4-methyl benzoquinoline (7 : 8), as well as their corresponding 3,3'-methylene bis-derivatives (1' to 6').

Class (A)-Acetoacet series : 3', 3; 4', 4; 7', 7; 6', 6; 1', 1; 8', 8; 5', 5 and 2', 2 (I-IV).

Class (B)-Hydroxy quinoline series : 6', 6; 3', 3; 2', 2; 5', 5; 4', 4 and 1', 1 (V-VIII).

In class (A) series the compound bis-1' has a far higher intensity than mono-1, but the slopes are practically similar; and in bis-2' sharp minima and maxima are observed at 2580, 2800 and 3100 Å, but mono-2 shows general absorption (Plate I). The compound 3 has a maxima at 2520 but its bis-3' has no maxima, inspite of similar curves; the curves of 4 and 4' are similar, but the intensity of bis-4' is much higher (Plate II). A general absorption with 5 is seen, but its bis-5' has a clear maxima

Fig. 4

It has been observed that a definite hyperchromic effect is shown by the rise in the absorption intensity of the bis-compounds. From the results of intensity differences of each pair of compounds from minimum to maximum in the series can, accordingly, be placed in the following order :

at 2520Å and a higher intensity; whereas 6 has an intensity higher than that of 5; and the bis-6' has lower absorption intensity than that of bis-5'. But, both 6 and 6' show a maxima at about 2460 and 2480 Å° respectively (Plate III).

It can be observed from this that the mono-1 has a lower intensity absorption. Introduction of a $-CH_3$ group in para as in (3) increases the absorption at all wave-lengths, in contrast to $-CH_3$ group in ortho as in (2), where the absorption is increased in near U.V. and decreased in far U.V., which may probably be due to steric effect. If two $-CH_3$ groups are introduced as in (4), it is queer to note that absorption intensity decreases than that in 3, which has one $-CH_3$ group in para position. If ortho $-CH_3$ group is replaced by Cl group in ortho as in (5), where it is characterised by lower absorption than that is found in (2); while in (6) the chlorine atom in meta increases the absorption to some extent and allows transition near 2470\AA .

Fig. 5

In the corresponding bis-compounds it is seen that the bis-1' shows general absorption, but the introduction of CH_3 group in ortho on both sides as in (2') increases the intensity as well as allows clear maxima and minima. If the same $-CH_3$ is in para as in (3'), the influence of both parts on each other seems to decrease with the result that maxima and minima are lost. With two $-CH_3$ groups in 4' the intensity becomes still lower than that with one $-CH_3$ group either in ortho or para position. The bis-5' allows maxim at 2500\AA (shift from 2800\AA), but the intensity is higher in beginning lower towards visible; whereas bis 6' lowers the intensity.

These results indicate that a considerable increase in the absorption intensity takes place, when certain groups like $-CH_3$; $-Cl$, etc., are substituted in the ortho position in presence of another group in para position in benzene or quinoline nucleus. Similar systematic difference due to the presence and proximity of certain groups would be observed on the

comparison of the hyperchromic effect with the corresponding pairs of known compounds, viz., β -naphthol and bis-(2-hydroxy- α -naphthyl)-methane; β -naphthylamine and 2-amino-2-hydroxy-1, 1' dinaphthyl methane; gramine methiodide and its methylene bis-derivative; benzene and dinaphthyl methane; toluene and 9,10-dihydroanthracene. (Plates 9 to 13 not shown here). The hyperchromic effect seen here from the increased absorption intensity and the trend in the extinction coefficient of absorption bands

Fig. 6

in the bis-series of compounds, when compared with those of their corresponding mono-derivatives, furnishes an interesting subject for further studies.

Experimental

Acetoacetylarnides and 2-hydroxy-4-methylquinolines have been prepared according to the method of Ewins and King¹⁰. Methylene bis-(acetoacetylarnides) and 3,3'-methylene bis-(2-hydroxy-4-methyl quinolines) have been synthesised by the methods of Mehta and Patel¹¹. All the spectra were taken on Beckmann Spectrophotometer BU Model and ethyl alcohol has been used as a solvent.

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